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Individualized, self-directed learning in a Bachelor's degree course

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INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a pilot module carried out within the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences & Arts Bachelor study program Business Engineering / Innovation. The primary objective of developing this 3 ECTS elective was to ascertain to what degree modules can cater to the needs of individual students and how these participants can be actively involved in the development of the module's content.

There are essential differences between the way a person acquires knowledge and skills at university and later on in his/her professional working environment. In particular, university courses hardly involve students in the design of a module's

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orientation and content, which would allow them to co-determine learning objectives and key aspects of the learning process.

The basic concept of the pilot module consisted in having each and every student participant specify his/her thematic orientation at the start with dedicated learning coaches and content experts. This served as the foundation for the continuous planning of the module's contents in line with the students' individual needs. The students themselves were held responsible for acquiring the chosen content, the coaches and experts taking on only a supporting role. In this novel learning scenario lecturers were thus *coaching* learners rather than solely imparting knowledge.

A further objective of the pilot module was to determine whether and how instruction can be individualized for larger groups of students and if individualized instruction has a positive influence on the learning behavior of students at tertiary level.

The learning processes of students in educational (tertiary-level) institutions differ significantly from those in which adults engage in professional (work-place) settings. In a professional setting learning is generally motivated by and closely associated with a concrete assignment, and the learner's compilation of content from various subject areas as he/she tackles this assignment resembles the work of an artist creating a mosaic. The pilot module creates a learning situation which corresponds more closely to the needs and approaches of the working professional. A prospective module, which will be discussed briefly later in this paper, will provide learning guidance to students carrying out industrial projects.

This paper first presents the theoretical background of the pilot module, followed by a description of the underlying methodology. Findings of the module evaluation are then presented. The final sections reflect on and discuss the methodological approach as well as potential improvements and the further development of the module.

1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE MODULE CONCEPT

For some years now, educators have been turning from traditional motivational psychology towards theories which focus on the attainment of goals. Early on, motivational theorists such as Deci and Ryan [1] shifted their interest from the effects of external influences on motivation to the subject's self-direction. According to their well-known Self-Determination Theory, motivation is derived from three universal, innate psychological needs: competence, autonomy and social integration. Subjects are more motivated to take action a) if they believe their behavior will afford them greater competence (self-efficacy), b) the more freedom they have in initiating and implementing a certain behavior (autonomy) and c) the more social interaction or connectedness the behavior fosters (gain in interpersonal relatedness).

The pilot module presented here satisfies each of these psychological needs: The module relies not only on the initiative of participants but in particular on their efficacy; greater autonomy is the core concept of the module; and social interaction and connectedness developed among the module participants, who have several extensive group meetings.

The engineer's prospective professional environment is growing ever more complex due to the fast pace of technological change and, especially, digitalization. Consequently, engineers must acquire new strategies to develop their competencies [2]. Traditional tertiary institutions no longer live up to these challenges [3]. They must not only impart knowledge but also competences required for autonomous learning and self-organization.

One acquires the ability to organize oneself primarily through exercising self-organization. Relevant academic literature refers to educational settings designed to foster self-organizational competence as »self-directed learning« [4] or, often synonymously, as »self-organized learning« (»SOL«). Deitering [4] proved empirically that the shift to self-directed learning is challenging for both teachers and learners and entails more than a simple replacement of one methodology with another.

There is no standard definition for SOL or self-directed learning. "Nonetheless, the approaches have a common denominator: Their focus is on the learner, who initiates and organizes his own learning processes. Objectives such as the promotion of self-determination, self-directed activity and responsibility for one's own learning process are to be found in many approaches." [4]

Examples of SOL applied to a specific, common task or mission especially worth mentioning are the Action Learning [5] and Team Academy [6] theories.

The pilot module did not provide a common group assignment, as is the focus in the Action Learning and Team Academy approaches, in order to afford students the greatest possible degree of freedom designing their learning projects. However, this focus on a common group project is to be integrated in a prospective pilot module.

The terms SOL and self-determined learning are not discussed in Hattie und Andermann's definitive guide to tertiary teaching and learning [7]. The module presented here may be regarded as an attempt to fill this gap in that it implements the SOL approach and tests its realization and efficacy at tertiary level.

2 TEACHING METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology underlying the design and implementation of the pilot module.

2.1 Selection of student participants

Interested students were invited to attend two orientations prior to registration for the term. In order to participate in these orientations students had to submit a statement in advance, describing in key words the topic which they wished to tackle, conveying their exceptional motivation and declaring their goals.

The objectives of the two orientations were:

- to consolidate students' personal goals
- to group students with similar learning objectives and/or objectives that promised synergetic potential
- to identify unsuitable topics and students with insufficient motivation.

2.2 Establishment of learning objectives

The first assignment of the term was to write a personal success story. The 12 enrolled students were to describe the specific situation which they wished to be able to master after completing the module. This success story also served as the basis for the final module exam. The following is a sample success story.

I have created a new corporate design for an association, a company or an organization, which I have implemented in various marketing instruments such as a homepage, business card and advertising posters. I have utilized my fundamental knowledge to generate a clean, positive image. Monitoring the homepage with analytical tools has allowed me to evaluate the initial reaction of potential target groups. Several possible marketing instruments are presented, from which the client can select the option he prefers.

Fig. 1. Sample success story

Subsequently, the students contemplated which competences they would need to acquire in order to accomplish their success story. This reflection led to the formulation of individual learning objectives. An example is presented in figure 2.

I am structuring my learning objectives according to Bloom's Cognitive Taxonomy. ...
I wish to attain Levels 1 and 2 (knowledge and comprehension) with respect to the development of a corporate design. ...
Regarding logos and the design of homepages I wish to attain Level 6: I want to be able to evaluate logos and homepages and to develop solutions myself. ...

Fig. 2. Extract from sample learning objectives

2.3 The learning process and evaluation of learning progress

Each student was assigned a content expert possessing expertise in the content area chosen. These four content experts had two tasks: a) to assess the success story and individual learning objectives: They determined whether the learning objectives were sufficiently challenging but also manageable within the scope of a 3 ECTS module; b) assessment of their students' achievement in the final module examination.

In addition, the students committed themselves to a minimum of two coaching sessions with the two learning coaches, in which they reflected on their learning process and, if appropriate, adjusted their course of action.

In two steering meetings the students presented the current status of their learning projects to their classmates and obtained peer feedback in open discussions.

2.4 Assessment

Assessment was two-fold, consisting in the assessment of the acquired professional expertise on the one hand and of the acquired learning competencies on the other. Each component carried a weight of 50%.

For the oral examination of their professional expertise each student first presented his/her own success story along with the results they achieved, the strategy they had chosen and the methods employed. An in-depth examination of their expertise followed. The students themselves contemplated and decided in advance what they wanted to present in order to prove their mastery of the content. They simulated a situation which corresponded to their success story.

In the final part of the professional competence examination the student's content expert and the learning coach asked clarification questions. The success story and the learning objectives derived from it served as benchmarks for the assessment of the student's newly acquired expertise.

The assessment of acquired learning competencies also consisted in three parts. First, each student presented and then reflected on their learning process. Subsequently, they estimated the grade they felt they deserved for their performance in the examination of their professional expertise. Discrepancies between their self-assessment and the experts' assessment were discussed.

Thirdly, the coaches presented the student with a new learning situation, which he/she was asked to structure. In this transfer task the student demonstrated his/her overall gain in professional and learning competence.

3 MODULE EVALUATION

Throughout its entire course, students evaluated the pilot module quantitatively with respect to five categories: personal motivation, relevance of the module to their professional future, learning gain (benefit in terms of the amount learned), satisfaction with their own learning progress, and support in the learning process. Furthermore, the module was evaluated qualitatively by the students and the content experts as well as by an external audit team consisting of didactics experts. This section presents the major findings of these evaluations.

In all five categories assessed quantitatively, the pilot module was ranked more favorably compared to all other modules in which the participating students were enrolled. Prominently, motivation was consistently considerably stronger throughout the semester in the pilot module than the average motivation in the other modules. This may be attributed on the one hand to the students' self-determination of their learning objectives and process, which were also emphasized in the qualitative evaluation. On the other hand, one must take into consideration that this module is an elective, deliberately chosen by the participants, as opposed to compulsory modules, which accounted for a certain portion of the other ('control') modules.

The evaluation of the module's relevance to the student's professional future also stood out. From the outset, ranking of the module's relevance was above average, even improving slightly toward the end of the semester. Here, too, there is a distinct difference between the pilot module and the average of the other modules the participants were taking. In their qualitative evaluations, students explained that the pilot module affords the opportunity to cultivate specific competencies which allow them to develop their personal professional profile.

The greatest changes from beginning to end of the semester were observed in the categories 'learning gain' and 'satisfaction with learning progress'. Whereas the pilot module was ascribed an average ranking compared with other modules in both categories at the outset, its ranking rose steadily in the course of the semester and was ultimately above-average for both aspects. The initial 'average' evaluation in these categories was an issue discussed in the final module exam. These discussions revealed that it was difficult for some students initially to actively promote and assess their own learning progress, despite clearly defined learning objectives. This issue also manifests itself in the evaluation of the module's 'support of the learning process': Though ranked slightly higher than the other modules on average, the comparatively wide spread of rankings shows that some students felt better and some less well supported in their learning efforts by the design of the module.

The qualitative evaluation indicates that the students would have appreciated receiving support in their learning processes from an earlier stage of their work, and that the content experts could and would gladly work more closely with the students earlier in the semester. The students, the content experts, the learning coaches and the audit team applauded the opportunity participants have to develop their individual personal profile in the pilot module. Further positive features of the module highlighted by the coaches and the audit team in the qualitative evaluation were the promotion of self-responsibility and the implementation of the self-reflective learning approach.

4 DISCUSSION

The first trial run of the pilot module proved that undergraduate students are capable of formulating and realizing their own individual learning projects. As opposed to traditional course modules, the lecturers here hand over to the students the full responsibility for determining the thematic orientation of their work, defining their learning objectives and organizing their learning process.

In the analysis of the realization of the module, the following were identified as critical success factors for this radical reversal of responsibility for learning:

- **High student motivation:** The students saw the module as an opportunity to develop specific individual personal competencies and extend them according to their personal preferences.
- **Acceptance of professional challenge:** High motivation incites students to set themselves challenging learning objectives. They are thus also willing to accept an expert's pertinent critique of their professional expertise and are motivated to prove their newly acquired competencies on completion of their learning project.
- **Reflection on the learning process:** The students must be given the space in which to reflect on and discuss their own learning process. This may take place within the group of student participants or in a dedicated coaching session with a learning coach.
- **Professional relevance:** In order to be capable of defining their own personal learning objectives, students must first contemplate the purpose of their learning efforts, for example by writing a personal success story in which they describe how the learning project is to advance their professional expertise. It is essential that the learning project be coupled with the individual's professional aspirations early on to ensure the student's motivation and goal-oriented dedication to his/her project.

- **From lecturer to content expert and to learning coach:** In contrast to traditional courses, the student's individual goals and learning objectives form the basis for the relationship between content experts / learning coaches and students. Reflection on the learning process, the generation and implementation of a learning evaluation scheme, and guidance in evaluating goal achievement take the place of imparting knowledge. There is only selective content support through appropriate content experts.

These positive conclusions are complemented by the issues listed below, which could not or only partially be addressed or resolved:

- **Selection of student participants:** Interested students were able to inform themselves about the module and generate initial ideas for their learning project in the two orientations. What ultimately motivated students to opt for or out of the module was not investigated.
- **Integration of the pilot module in the study program:** To which degree the competencies acquired in the pilot module might be transferred to further courses or project modules has not been clarified. This is a subject of the study program's continuous curricular development process.
- **Qualification of the content experts and learning coaches:** Prerequisites for commitment as a content expert or learning coach have not been specified. For the pilot module to be anchored in the curriculum the prerequisite competencies would need to be described systematically and a program would need to be designed and initiated to develop these competencies in lecturers.
- **Transfer of self-direction and self-organization to industrial projects**
As argued in the introduction, learning in a professional setting is normally induced by the challenge of a specific assignment. A prospective pilot module should investigate how students can develop self-regulatory competencies in the context of an industrial project. The students are to autonomously acquire an industrial project assignment requiring team work. Task resolution is driven by the individuals' self-defined learning objectives on the one hand and, of overriding importance, the personal goals formulated in their success stories.

The form of individualized instruction presented here allows students to develop their personal professional profile to enhance their career prospects or simply to study a topic in-depth. In this setting the students reflect on their learning strategies and consciously expand their capability to learn autonomously. The content experts and learning coaches take on an unfamiliar role in which they concern themselves with the personal needs of the individual student and are called on to support and facilitate the student's learning process. Various features of traditional educational settings that have heretofore been taken for granted are overthrown. It is, for instance, a novel experience to see students participate in the design of their own final exam in which they must prove their mastery of the self-defined module content.

The pilot module demonstrates for the study program, for the entire university and for undergraduate studies in general that teaching and learning can be effective beyond the conventions of knowledge transfer. The module prepares students for their prospective learning in professional settings by exacting a high degree of self-

directed learning competency. The module provides a sheltered setting in which the unique learning process of each and every student is facilitated through the pertinent guidance of content experts and learning coaches. Innovative learning scenarios such as this can distinguish a study program as well as an entire university.

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